

Factors affecting the personal development of school-age children**Matyaqubova Fotima Urinbayevna**

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada maktab yoshidagi bolalarning o'qish faoliyati, qiziqish va harakatchanligi, ulardagi aqliy taraqqiyot shahsiy rivojlanishiga tasir etuvchi omillar, oquvchilarda qiziqishlar, aqliy taraqqiyot, shahsiy rivojlanishi va ularning ahamiyati haqida malumot beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: aqliy rivojlanish, o'quvchi, kichik maktab yoshi, qiziqish, mustaqil fikrlash, malaka va ko'nikma.

Аннотация: В статье представлена информация об учебной активности, интересе и подвижности детей школьного возраста, факторах, влияющих на их психическое развитие и развитие личности, интересах, психическом развитии, развитии личности и их значении у учащихся

Ключевые слова: психическое развитие, школьник, младший школьный возраст, интерес, самостоятельное мышление, компетентность и умения.

Abstract: The article provides information on the study activity, interest and mobility of school-age children, factors affecting their mental development and personal development, interests, mental development, personal development and their importance in students.

Key words: mental development, student, junior school age, interest, independent thinking, competence and skills.

Elementary school students are gullible, susceptible to external impressions.

As mentioned by our great omens, a person's character is formed more than anything else in the first years of his life, and the qualities that appear in him during this period become a person's second nature. The whole responsibility for the formation of moral norms for the formation of natural feelings and qualities in the second nature of a person falls on the primary school teacher. In this period of the child, every word, every action of the teacher acts as a criterion of truth for him. Because students strongly believe in teachers. They listen to his opinions. They are described seriously in their pedagogical sophistication. They always follow the requirements. They strive to fulfill the tasks given by him. To learn to think correctly, to refrain from inappropriate behavior and to listen to music. In order to achieve the goal of developing the moral qualities of elementary school students, it is necessary to take into account their age and psychological characteristics.

Study activity creates important conditions for the development of intelligence, sensitivity, observation, memory and recall capabilities of a student of junior school age, forms calculation skills. The sharpness of perception, clarity, purity, clarity, vividness of imagination, strength of memory, and clarity of thinking of a child of this age are distinguished from children of other ages by their curiosity and trustworthiness. Engaging in reading activities during the junior school period, including getting to know the various properties of material things, has a great impact on the growth of senses. Children of primary school age develop especially quickly the ability to distinguish, see and hear. It has been determined by Russian scientists that the perception of colors in children aged 7-10 years increases by 45%, and in children up to 10-12 years, it increases by 65%. Teaching

young schoolchildren to draw has a great impact on the growth of color sensitivity. The sensitivity to distinguish tones grows strongly, especially in the process of teaching children music and singing. In the growth of senses, physical training is also very important. Exercises that involve precise movement develop children's motor skills. By the time of junior high school, all types of perception improve in terms of content, accuracy, and clarity mainly due to education. Children of this age are sharply different from people of other ages with their clarity, fluency, and sharpness of perception. They have the opportunity to acquire important features of perception due to their attention to everything.

It is known that the psychological characteristics of students are different, and the means of educational influence used successfully for one student may not give the expected result when used together with another. There is no doubt that better results will be achieved if educational activities are carried out individually. Implementation of these tasks depends on how well the teacher has learned the characteristics of students. Being able to find a reasonable way to the mental world of each student in the educational process is a guarantee of success.

In the process of education and upbringing, it is necessary to organize the life and activities of children in such a way that the characteristics of the child's personality are enriched and strengthened. Inquisitive interests in the first years of school education, the interest in knowing the surrounding world significantly develops more intellectual curiosity.

Psychologists say that at first interests are formed in relation to some facts, events that can be separated from other things. In reading activities, the mental processes of young students are activated by their curiosity to know, interest

appears on the basis of the mental activity of students and further develops this mental activity of students as a personal individual. Students' interests are diverse in terms of content and stability. A wide range of meaningful and stable interests begin to emerge from a young age.

It is known that students of I-II classes do not have clear interests yet, students are interested in everything during their studies. They are satisfied with their own activities. Later, a great interest develops to find out the reasons, laws, connections and connections between events. If I-II graders ask "What is this?" - question is more interesting, for older children "Why?", "How?" questions remain important. With the development of reading skills, there is an interest in reading books. First, there is an interest in reading books, then in reading specific literature and fairy tales, and later in reading books about not difficult scientific adventures. I-II graders begin to be attracted by the content of the material they are learning, some methods of study work. Independence of III and IV grade students grows. Pupils of this age begin to be interested in all activities related to the development of mental activity methods, memory, speech, attention and will. In the fourth grade, students clearly define their interests in various subjects. If they like it by paying more attention to some of the subjects, they don't like some. Pupils will be interested in the work they enjoy the most. A child should not lose confidence in himself while doing certain work, he should understand that he can do the work assigned to him, and for this he needs to show enthusiasm. The correct arrangement of education and training and recreation of students is important for the stability of students' interests. Adults should pay attention to the interests of students. Children's positive interests should be encouraged and encouraged by

adults. Teachers and parents who do not pay attention to their favorite activity, which is always attractive to them, are bad pedagogues and bad educators. A teacher is the best ideal of a student's life. A teacher who always strives forward and lives with meaningful and broad interests helps students to develop high spiritual interests and intellectual development. In addition, interest in technology, modern technology, the newest type of car, airplane, and computer will quickly form. Pupils of III and IV classes of rural schools begin to show their interest in agriculture. Children willingly feed birds and pets and begin to collect information about them. This affects the development of children's knowledge. The development of interest in reading in children of primary school age directly depends on the organization of education. Therefore, the teacher should consider the laws of the development of interests in elementary school students. Students' interests and mental development progress from simple to complex, from known to unknown, from close to far, from description to explanation, from facts to generalization. Attention should be paid to the following aspects of students' mastery of education:

- The younger the students, the more demonstrative the education and active action plays a big role.

All students do not have the same knowledge, they have different levels of preparation and it cannot be otherwise. Therefore, lack of familiarity with the given material may not indicate the real cause of low mastery.

We know that many pedagogues find it difficult to assess the mental development of students, and as a result, an important factor that should be taken into account in the educational process is left out of their work.

It should be noted that the level of mental development of students is not determined only by their ability to acquire theoretical or practical knowledge or the presence of knowledge. The level of mental development of the student is the development of thought processes, the ability to distinguish between the important and the basic ones of the educational material, the ability to transfer the acquired knowledge or the acquired and mastered skills to other activities, the ability to apply various theoretical knowledge in practice, independent thinking. , is determined by several signs, such as the ability to draw conclusions.

In conclusion, the opinions and opinions of the third grade students differ from the opinion opinions in terms of content, form, and structure. This is due to the fact that the scope of their life experience is wider, and there are also differences in the way of revealing the essence of the problem, different approaches to things, and the difference depending on the characteristics of the age period. In order for students of I-III grades to find the content of moral concepts, it is necessary to first find generalizing secondary signs of distinguishing the important signs of each concept.

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